

Inclusive Education: Where Power Resides in the Powerless

Poonam Mishra

Associate Professor, Department of Education,
DAV Degree College, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India
Email: poonam8263@gmail.com

Received : 12/05/2022

1st BPR : 21/05/2022

2nd BPR : 30/05/2022

Accepted : 07/06/2022

Abstract

Inclusive education is the need of the hour. It helps build relationships and inculcate mutual respect and understanding. There is a growing consensus that people with disabilities should be included in development programmes, as the exclusion to date of this marginalized group will probably result in the non-achievement of the UN Millennium Commission's broadly inclusive global development agenda. This paper, while limited by the lack of available empirical data and constraints of desk research aims to present a case study of the current status of inclusive education in India with a focus on children with disabilities. The paper analyses the inclusion in Indian perspective, its holistic vision, principles of inclusion, common practices in inclusive classroom, benefits of inclusion, teacher training in special education and role of NGO's followed by the discussion of the implications these may have for the future of educational inclusion of all children. This paper may prove useful for anyone wishing to undertake empirical research in this, until recently, neglected field or simply needing to gain an overview of the educational situation in India.

Keywords: Education

Inclusion a Holistic Vision:

Our society has witnessed many changes from time to time. One of the most debated changes in past few years is "inclusive education". Any child may experience a special need during the course of educational years (UNESCO). Some children feel 'left-outs' and never enter school or enter only for a few years and, as repeaters, become 'drop-outs' or, more correctly 'pushed-outs', without their needs having been met. These children are a vivid illustration of the failure of schools to teach rather than the pupils' failure to learn. A school system emphasizing Education for All should ensure the right of all children to a meaningful education based on individual needs and abilities (Ture Johnson 2002). Inclusive education means that all students are attended and they are welcomed by their neighborhood schools in age-appropriate. Further, regular classes are supported for all to learn, contribute and participate in all aspects of the life of the school. The Right to Education (RTE) Act, introduced in 2012 also allows children with special needs to pursue mainstream education. All students, irrespective of their impairment, should be educated in mainstream schools. To put this very simply, children with visual impairment, low vision, hearing impairment, leprosy-cured, locomotor disability, mental retardation, mental illness, autism, cerebral palsy and multiple disability have the right to study in a regular school environment till the age of 18 years. (Ref. RTE Act.). Inclusive Education is important because we value our diverse communities. These communities start at school, where all students learn to live alongside peers. They learn together; they play together; they grow and are nurtured together. Inclusion in education describes an approach wherein students with special educational needs spend most or all of their time with non-disabled students. Inclusion was once thought only necessary for educating students with special educational needs until dual certification of special educators as school teacher leaders. Now it is crucial that all of teachers ensure inclusive practices for all students in their classroom and the wider school. It might lead to the need of reforming the school system as a whole from a traditional, examination-oriented to an inclusive,

child-oriented approach. Implementation of inclusion practice requires selection of students with mild to severe special needs.

Inclusive theory V/S Exclusive theory

Exclusion theory works on the unstated underlying assumptions, that: We are not all equal in capacity or value. It is not feasible to give equal opportunity. We must choose and thus train an elite who will take care of the rest. The weaker sections of the society will benefit through the trickle-down theory. Whereas, the inclusion theory works on the assumptions that we are unique in value; however, each has unique capacity. All people can learn. All people have contributions to make. We have a responsibility and an opportunity to give every person the chance to make a contribution. The criterion for inclusion is breathing, not IQ, income, colour, race, sex or language. It is unethical, politically unacceptable and repugnant to write off marginalized people in our society.

The principle of inclusive education was adopted at the "World Conference on Special Needs

Education: Access and Quality" (Salamanca, Spain 1994) and was restated at the World Education Forum (Dakar, Senegal 2000). The idea of inclusion is further supported by the United Nation's Standard Rules on Equalization of Opportunities for Person with Disability Proclaiming Participation and equality for all. Of late, a consensus has emerged among Indian intellectuals and pedagogues for adopting inclusive education in mainstream schools (Sanjeev and Kumar, 2007). Inclusive education is about how we develop and design our schools, classrooms, programs and activities so that all students learn and participate together.

India was a signatory to the Salamanca Statement. In this perspective the Human Resource

Development minister of India Sri Arjun Singh on the 21st March 2005 assured in the Rajya Sabha that MHRD has formulated a comprehensive action plan for the Inclusive Education of Children and Youth with Disabilities (Sanjeev and Kumar, 2007). The government is committed to provide education through mainstream schools for children with disabilities in accordance with PWD ACT, 1995 and all the schools in the country will be made disabled friendly by 2020. Rupees 10 billion have been outlaid to fulfill the needs of disabled persons between the ages of 14 and 18 years through a revised plan for Inclusive Education of Children and Youth with Disabilities (IECYD). In 2005-06, the Project Approval Board has allocated an amount of Rs.187.79 crores under this component for a total 20.14 lakh Children With Special Needs (CWSN) identified. The commitment of the Government of India to Universalisation of Elementary Education (UEE) cannot be fully achieved without taking care of special educational needs of the physically and mentally challenged children.

Regular inclusion v/s Full inclusion

Inclusion has two sub-types: the first is sometimes called regular inclusion or partial inclusion, and the other is full inclusion.

"Inclusive practice" is not always inclusive but is a form of integration. For example, students with special needs are educated in regular classes for nearly all of the day, or at least for more than half of the day. Whenever possible, the students receive any additional help or special instruction in the general classroom, and the student is treated like a full member of the class. However, most specialized services are provided outside a regular classroom, particularly if these services require special equipment or might be disruptive to the rest of the class (such as speech therapy), and students are pulled out of the regular classroom for these services. In this case, the student occasionally leaves the regular classroom to attend smaller, more intensive instructional sessions in a resource room, or to receive other related services, such as speech and language therapy, occupational and/or physical therapy, psychological services, and social work (Bowe, 2005). He further opined that, this approach can be very similar to many mainstreaming practices, and may differ in little more than the educational ideals behind it.

In the "full inclusion" setting, the students with special needs are always educated alongside students without special needs, as the first and desired option while maintaining appropriate supports and services. Some educators say this might be more effective for the students with special needs (Feldman,2008). At the extreme, full inclusion is the integration of all students, even those that require the most substantial educational and behavioral supports and services to be successful in regular classes and the elimination of special, segregated special education classes. Special education is considered a service, not a place and those services are integrated into the daily routines classroom structure, environment, curriculum and strategies and brought to the student, instead of removing the student to meet his or her individual needs. However, this approach to full inclusion is somewhat controversial, and it is not widely understood or applied to date ((Feldman, 2008); (Hastings and Oakford,2003); (Kavale, 2002); (Praisner,2003)).

Principles of Inclusion and Necessary Resources

Although once hailed, usually by its opponents, as a way to increase achievement while decreasing costs, full inclusion does not save money, but is more cost-beneficial and cost-effective. It is not designed to reduce students' needs, and its first priority may not even be to improve academic outcomes; in most cases, it merely moves the special education professionals (now dual certified for all students in some states) out of "their own special education" classrooms and into a corner of the general classroom or as otherwise designed by the "teacher-in-charge" and "administrator-in-charge". To avoid harm to the academic education of students with disabilities, full panoply of services and resources is required (of education for itself), including:

- Adequate supports and services for the student
- Well-designed individualized education programs
- Professional development for all teachers involved, general and special educators alike
- Time for teachers to plan, meet, create, and evaluate the students together
- Reduced class size based on the severity of the student needs
- Professional skill development in the areas of cooperative learning, peer tutoring, adaptive curriculum
- Collaboration between parents or guardians, teachers or para educators, specialists, administration, and outside agencies.
- Sufficient funding so that schools will be able to develop programs for students based on student need instead of the availability of funding.

Common Practices in Inclusive Classrooms

Students in an inclusive classroom are generally placed with their chronological age-mates, regardless of whether the students are working above or below the typical academic level for their age. Also, to encourage a sense of belonging, emphasis is placed on the value of friendships. Teachers often nurture a relationship between a student with special needs and a same-age student without a special educational need. Another common practice is the assignment of a buddy to accompany a student with special needs at all times (for example in the cafeteria, on the playground, on the bus and so on). This is used to show students that a diverse group of people make up a community, that no one type of student is better than another, and to remove any barriers to a friendship that may occur if a student is viewed as "helpless." Such practices (Strully and Strully, 1996) reduce the chance for elitism among students in later grades and encourage cooperation among groups.

Teachers use a number of techniques to help build classroom communities:

- Using games designed to build community

- Involving students in solving problems
- Sharing songs and books that teach community
- Openly dealing with individual differences by discussion
- Assigning classroom jobs that build community
- Teaching students to look for ways to help each other
- Utilizing physical therapy equipment such as standing frames, so students who typically use wheelchairs can stand when the other students are standing and more actively participate in activities
- Encouraging students to take the role of teacher and deliver instruction (e.g. read a portion of a book to a student with severe disabilities)
- Focusing on the strength of a student with special needs
- Create classroom checklists
- Take breaks when necessary
- Create an area for children to calm down
- Organize student desk in groups
- Create a self and welcoming environment
- Set ground rules and stick with them
- Help establish short-term goals
- Design a multi-faced curriculum
- Communicate regular with parents and/or caregivers
- Seek support from other special education teachers

Benefits of Inclusive Education

All children benefit from inclusive education. It allows them to:

- Develop individual strengths and gifts, with high and appropriate expectations for each child.
- Work on individual goals while participating in the life of the classroom with other students their own age.
- Involve their parents in their education and in the activities of their local schools.
- Foster a school culture of respect and belonging. Inclusive education provides opportunities to learn about and accept individual differences, lessening the impact of harassment and bullying.
- Develop friendships with a wide variety of other children, each with their own individual needs and abilities.
- Positively affect both their school and community to appreciate diversity and inclusion on a broader level.

Factors determining the success of inclusive classrooms:

- Family-school partnerships
- Collaboration between general and special educators
- Well-constructed plans that identify specific accommodations, modifications, and goals for each student
- Coordinated planning and communication between "general" and "special needs" staff

- Integrated service delivery
- Ongoing training and staff development
- Leadership of teachers and administrators

Relationship to Progressive Education

Some advocates of inclusion promote the adoption of progressive education practices. In the progressive education or inclusive classroom, everyone is exposed to a "rich set of activities," and each student does what he or she can do, or what he or she wishes to do and learns whatever comes from that experience. Maria Montessori's schools sometimes named as an example of inclusive education.

Inclusion requires some changes in how teachers teach, as well as changes in how students with and without special needs interact with and relate to one another. Inclusive education practices frequently rely on active learning, authentic assessment practices, applied curriculum, multi-level instructional approaches, and increased attention to diverse student needs and individualization.

Teacher training in Special Education (SE)

In India teacher training in special education is imparted through both face-to-face and distance mode. There is provision for pre-service teacher training in Special Education, but it is mainly concentrated in secondary level training. There are 159 institutions of secondary teacher training in SE whereas there are only eleven institutions in the country that imparts pre-service training at elementary or primary level in SE. The Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) is the apex authority to develop, recognize and regulate the course curriculum of SE. The Madhya Pradesh Bhoj (Open) University, Bhopal is the single university in the country, imparting B. Ed. (SE) through distance learning mode. Recently, it has launched Post Graduate Professional Diploma in Special Education Course for general B.Ed. students.

Successful candidate of this program becomes equivalent to B.Ed.-SEDE degree holder with specialization in opted disability area. As the Indian school system is one of the largest in the world and number of CWSN are very high, the prevailing situation of pre-service teacher training in special education needs to be strengthened or elaborate alternative mechanism for incorporating the elements of special education in general teacher training programs needs to found out. The teacher training course curriculum of general pre-service training programs neither fully equips the teachers and teacher educators to deal with the CWSN nor it equip them to manage the mild and moderately disabled children in general classrooms. Towards this end, an MOU has been signed between the National Council for Teacher Educations (NCTE) and the Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) leading towards a convergence so as to sensitize all teachers and resource persons. The NCERT (2000) has set up a group under the National Curriculum Framework Review to examine the pedagogic inputs and classroom reorganization required for CWSN. Even, UGC National Educational Testing Bureau has already included "Special Education", in curriculum of its Educational discipline. It includes details about special education, integrated education, education of mentally retarded (MR), visually impaired (VI), hearing impaired (HI), orthopedically handicapped (OH), gifted and creative children, learning disabled children and education of Juvenile delinquents. The Postgraduate Departments of Education in India is on way to strengthen the disability element in their respective curriculum.

Role of NGO's

There are many international, national, and local NGOs involved with disability issues in India. Many local NGOs, while diverse and widespread, tend to be based on a charity/welfare approach (Thomas,

2004) and informed by the medical model (Hooja, cited in Mukhopadhyay, 2003). Although the exact number is unknown, there are at least 1,000 NGOs and voluntary organizations actively engaged in education (GOI, 2000), of which the government funded 701 with grants in aid in 2004-5 (GOI, 2005). Much more commonly, local educational agencies have the responsibility to organize services for children with disabilities. They may provide a variety of settings, from special classrooms to mainstreaming to inclusion, and assign, as teachers and administrators often do, students to the system that seems most likely to help the student achieve his or her individual educational goals. Students with mild or moderate disabilities, as well as disabilities that do not affect academic achievement, such as using power wheelchair, scooter or other mobility device, are most likely to be fully included; indeed, children with polio or with leg injuries have grown to be leaders and teachers in government and universities; self advocates travel across the country and to different parts of the world. However, students with all types of disabilities from all the different disability categories have been successfully included in general education classes, working and achieving their individual educational goals in regular school environments and activities.

Thus, education of children with disabilities in India, as all over the world, has moved from segregation, special schools to integrated education. There is a national level central government sponsored scheme called Integrated Education of Disabled Children (IEDC). This project was started in 1980s and designed based on the experience gathered from a UNICEF assisted pilot project called PIED (project on integrated education of disabled children). In the mid-1980s many NGOs implemented this IEDC with grants from government of India. This project is implemented by the Ministry of Human Resource Development. This is basically an itinerant resource teaching approach and one resource teacher was given to every 8 children with special needs. There are around 60,000 children with disabilities getting access to education under this scheme (Katharine, 2007). By and large the project is managed by the NGO sector.

NGOs are perceived by the government as widening the implementation network and bringing flexibility and innovation into education programmes. In fact, they are currently implementing much of the IEDC scheme, as the job of including children with disabilities in education nationwide is too vast for the government to be able to undertake alone (Mukhopadhyay, 2003). (NGOs) "are important stakeholders in social development programmes...[and] are also a repository of knowledge of grassroots realities because of their proximity to the people" (GOI, 2000: 17).

Many national and local NGOs support special institutions, perhaps because it is easier to raise public support for residential centres than the promotion of inclusive education (ESCAP, 2001). However, a NGO that combines both specialist and inclusive aims is the National Association for the Blind (NAB). With branches nationwide, the NAB facilitates integration with skill and resource support (Julka, 2005). While it can be criticized for its roots in the medical model, it is important to remember that the specialist support they provide can assist with literacy (through Braille) and mobility (with a cane) for the mainstream classroom and beyond.

Some NGOs have metamorphosed their specialist institutions into resource centers in order to support inclusive education (Katharine, 2007). For example, the Spastics Society of India (SSI) advocates for better understanding that many children with cerebral palsy do not have learning disabilities. The head office has also become a 'National Resource Centre for Inclusion' (funded by the Canadian International Development Agency, CIDA) for all children marginalized from learning, including girls and working children, operating inclusive pre-school classrooms in Mumbai's slum areas². In addition, they offer a postgraduate diploma in inclusive education among other courses, in order to clarify this much-misunderstood concept. However, SSI's impact is currently mostly limited to the cities of Mumbai, Bangalore and Chennai.

Similarly, the Jesuit-run Divine Light Trust for the Blind near Bangalore has become a resource centre to train teachers in mainstream schools in order to encourage the inclusion of blind children in their classrooms (Coleridge, 1993).

International NGOs too have a role to play in the promotion of inclusive education. Some, such as Voluntary Service Overseas (VSO) and Action on Disability and Development (ADD), both DFID-funded, focus on advocacy through civil society movements. Save the Children UK (SCUK) operates in several states in northern India through local NGOs, with a focus on child rights (SCUK, 2004). They fund, for example, the Society for the Integrated Development of the Himalayas (SIDH) which has successfully supported the establishment of innovative community schools in remote mountain areas with scattered tribal populations and lack of physical access to government schools due to the local terrain (Crompton, 1999). While SIDH has had a positive impact on the inclusion of girls and tribal children in education, they do not appear to have encountered children with disabilities in any of the villages where they work (Katharine, 2007). Other international NGOs, such as Christoffel Blindenmission, do not work for attitudinal change so much as on the financial support of local hospitals with eye units in remote rural areas, rehabilitation centres, special schools and vocational centres for diverse disabilities run by local NGOs, many of which are Christian missionary-founded.

Implications

While there is no shortage of issues and constraints in the interpretation and implementation of inclusive education in India, it is important to remember that it is at a very early stage of conceptualization and implementation. The fact that it is being discussed and in some places implemented, albeit falteringly, demonstrates a willingness to engage with elements of a new concept that has the potential to be developed in the future in a positive manner. This section will explore the implications that these issues have for possible areas of development that could move forward mutual understandings of how inclusive education could benefit the Indian education system, or rather the people in it under four headings - Policy implementation, School quality, attitudinal change and Undertaking Research work on IE.

Policy Implementation

So long as the, "...struggle to achieve compulsory education for a majority of children takes precedence over meeting the needs of those with disabilities..." (Ainscow et al, 1995 cited in Singal, 2005b: 338), change for children with disabilities will continue to be sporadic and painfully slow. The division of educational responsibility for children, between the MSJE (Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment) for those with disabilities and the MHRD (Ministry of Human Resource Development) for those without, can only exacerbate (Katharine, 2007) this struggle, and highlight the 'different' nature of children with disabilities' needs and the special needs focus of inclusive education with it. This implies that if inclusive education came under one ministry alone, most probably the MHRD, potentially both conceptualization and implementation could be clarified and promoted, while the needs of children with disabilities could finally be mainstreamed (Katharine, 2007).

The absence of accountability mechanisms, which results in poor policy implementation, suggests that in order to ensure implementation of 1995's rhetorically positive Persons with Disabilities Act, some kind of legal enforcement mechanism needs to be created (Alur, 2002), perhaps related to resource allocation or government employee contract renewal. In turn, enforcement needs a disciplined inspection network of regular monitoring and evaluation by external evaluators (to avoid report corruption) in order to ascertain whether policy is indeed being implemented, and to what standard.

The size and diversity of India dictates the necessity for state governments to take the responsibility of implementing central policy. Not only does a lack of accountability contribute to the diversity of state performance in inclusive education, as with all policy, but also variations in local government administrative capacity can have a disparity-inducing effect. Training of government officials of all levels (GOI, 2000) for managing monitoring and evaluation systems or enforcing accountability are

just as important as training in conceptual awareness of inclusive education and disability issues. Management reform at the local level is essential for sustainability and long-term change, but in this context it depends on the political will of each state to instigate reform.

School Quality

As “disabling educational environments affect all children, not only those who are identified as having impairments,” (Miles, 2000: 11) it is essential that school quality issues are identified and addressed. The re-conceptualization of inclusive education as a school quality issue could have significant impact on educational change in India for all children. This suggests that with the reconceptualisation of inclusive education, from students with special needs to all children, school quality could improve nationwide.

Teacher education is certainly key to this metamorphosis, but without a wider understanding of the meaning of Inclusive Education for all learners (Panda, 2005), it will make little difference. This has been proved to date with the huge investment into government teacher training programmes that have yielded little long-term fruit in the shape of pedagogical revolution. The non-implementation of child-centred teaching methods may be influenced by a focus on theory rather than practice (Holdsworth, 1994), the brevity of teacher training courses without follow-up or feedback (Dyer, 2000), or simply a lack of basic teacher knowledge leading to insecurity that they will not be able to answer a question (Dyer, 2000). Nevertheless, this failure to change pedagogy is not only due to teacher education course design, but also the reality of 24.5% teacher absenteeism (World Bank, 2004), combined with resource-constrained institutions with large classes and an inflexible curriculum which force the teachers to return to didactic habits in order to cope. Croft (2006) however, suggests that class size need not be a hindrance in the practice of child-centered pedagogy if training takes into account the context-specific knowledge and methods teachers already use in their large, diverse classes, and progresses from this point.

A further hindrance to new pedagogy is that parental expectations are of exam results, not of ‘joyful learning’ (Katharine, 2007). Hence, the pressure on teachers is even greater to avoid change. This exam ‘backwash’ no doubt contributes to the notion of within-child deficit and faith in IQ (which has been discredited due to its over-reliance on access to conventional education in order to score highly (Thorpe & McKie, 2002) which can only be altered by attitudinal change aided by teacher education. For example, exam success from the practice of innovative teaching methodology, as demonstrated in the SIDH programme, can change attitudes towards child-centered pedagogy (Crumpton, 1999).

It is not only teachers who benefit from training, but local government administrators too, as their support and understanding of inclusive education could provide invaluable assistance to institutional innovation (Holdsworth, 1994). This reflects Miles’ (2000) belief that good working relationships are critical to the implementation of inclusive education. SCUK (Miles, 2002) recommends a whole school approach to the inclusion of children with disabilities, in that all teachers are consulted and trained, not a select few ‘specialists’. In addition, it is essential that teachers are supported not only by strong educational management with a clear strategy to improve school quality, but also by parents and the local community.

However, while Singal (2005a) criticizes government pragmatism in avoiding deeper inclusion issues by focusing on physical and sensory disabilities only as suitable for mainstream education, it is worth considering that with such a mountain to climb it may be better to start somewhere and then progress. Perhaps deeper reflection will come after the successful inclusion of a few.

Attitudinal Change

The context-specificity of the socio-religious construct is a factor that cannot be ignored when looking at the implications for the future of any aspect of life in India. However, the caste system will not disappear overnight, but it is a highly constructed world within which all implications must be considered and all potential change would take place.

While attitudes which are deep-rooted in cultural assumptions are probably the most difficult aspect of change, they have influence across the board, ranging from community, to school, to government. This suggests that (Katharine, 2007)attitudinal change should be considered an integral part of any inclusive education programme or plan, right from raising awareness at grass-roots level (including for parents), to teacher education (including sensitizing teachers to listen to the children's perspectives (Mukhopadhyay, nd), to administrative capacity-building, to policy-making.

As attitudes are based on beliefs, they can be changed when presented with new information such as inclusion success stories of children with disabilities. Islands of change may have limited coverage, but they can be scaled-up and lead to broader change with advocacy (Holdsworth, 1994). Community-based rehabilitation has also been found to assist in attitudinal change (Mukhopadhyay, nd).

Research

While there is a noticeable lack of in-depth empirical and academic research on inclusive education in India, this can also be seen as reflecting the preliminary stage such discussions are at in this context (Singal, 2005b) and the room for development of a constructive discourse with further research.

This absence of information suggests that there is a dire need for more research into both the implementation (Dyer, 2000) and impact of inclusive education in India. There are large gaps in the hard-to-access research, both qualitative and quantitative, on IE in India. The apparent desire for change hinted at by the slowly developing discussion around inclusive education at all levels, can only be fulfilled if it is planned for. In order to constructively implement inclusive education for all children, planning must not only be adapted according to context, but also include funding for continual research, monitoring and impact evaluation from all perspectives. This includes the children's voices, and especially from those with disabilities. The long-term filling of the current research gap in IE in India could make a significant contribution to a sustainable, adaptable process of change. Without research on inclusive education outcomes (Katharine, 2007), lessons-learned cannot be applied to make implementation more effective, and so schools more accessible to all learners

Conclusion

As a system, inclusive education should be flexible. Its principle should be education in the regular classroom whenever possible. This need for flexibility must be reflected in the methods and materials used to give these children the widest possible access to the regular curriculum. When discussing the kind of service needed, the starting point should always be what is best for the particular child. Emphasizing inclusive education does not rule out special schools or centres. They would still be required to cater to children with profound and complex difficulties in need of more specialized and extensive help, including e.g. many deaf children. This alternative should, however, not be considered, unless classroom placement cannot meet their needs. In line with the new policy of inclusive education, special schools begin to function more and more as resource centres. They involve in outreach programmes, where they draw on their vast experience and knowledge. They link their activities with those of the regular schools, the families, and the communities. Inclusive education services allow children with disabilities to stay with their family and to go to the nearest school, just like all other children. This circumstance is of vital importance to their personal development. Interrupting a disabled child's normal development may have far more severe consequences than the disability itself. In this context, it is important to stress the role parents have. They have a right to be involved in all decision-making concerning their child. They should be seen as partners in the education process. Where there is such co-operation, parents have been found to be very important resources for the teachers and the schools.

We all have the power to listen to voices that are seldom heard. If we choose to make the time, to learn to listen, and to struggle with the pain and frustration that disempowered people feel, we will

see new visions, feel new energy, and find hope in our future. There is power in the powerless. We can be catalysts, or encrusted residue. The choice is ours.

References

1. Alur, M. (2002) Introduction, in Hegarty, S & Alur M (eds) (2002) Education and Children with Special Needs: from Segregation to Inclusion, New Delhi: Sage Publications
2. Bowe, Frank. (2005). Making Inclusion Work. Merrill Education/Prentice Hall.
3. Coleridge, P. (1993) Disability, Liberation, and Development, Oxford: Oxfam
4. Croft, A. (2006) Prepared for Diversity? Teacher education for lower primary classes in Malawi, in Little, A. W. (ed) (2006) Education for All and Multigrade Teaching: challenges and opportunities, Netherlands: Springer, pp 103-126
5. Crumpton, B. (ed) (1999) Learning for Life in the Hills, in Molteno, M., Ogadhoh, K., Cain, E., & Crumpton, B. (eds) (1999) Towards Responsive Schools: supporting better schooling for disadvantaged children: case studies from Save the Children, London: DFID, Serial No. 38, pp 43-66
6. Dyer, C. (2000) Operation Blackboard: Policy Implementation in Indian Elementary Education, Oxford: Symposium Books
7. ESCAP (2001) Pathfinders: Towards Full Participation and Equality of Persons with Disabilities in the ESCAP Region, Part Three, Chapter IX: Integrated Education in Gujarat, (pp. 48-52) New York & Geneva: United Nations
8. Feldman, Robert S. (2008), "Understanding Psychology Eighth Edition", page 309. Retrieved 2010-06-10.
9. GOI (2000) India: Education For All Year 2000 Assessment, Ministry of Human Resource Development, New Delhi: Government of India and NIEPA
10. GOI (2005) Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment Annual Report 2004-05, New Delhi: Government of India
11. Hastings. R.P., & Oakford, S. (2003), Student teachers' attitudes toward the inclusion of children with special needs. Educational Psychology, , page 23, 87-95
12. Helander, E. (1993) Prejudice and Dignity. UNDP, N.Y.
13. Holdsworth, J. (1994) China, Integrated Education Project, Anhui Province, in Making it happen: Examples of good practice in Special Needs Education and Community-based Programmes, Paris: UNESCO, pp 14-24
14. Julka, A. (2005) Educational Provisions and Practices for Learners with Disabilities in India, paper presented at the Inclusive and Supportive Education Congress 2005, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow
15. Katharine Giffard-Lindsay,(2007), "Inclusive Education in India: Interpretation, Implementation, and Issues", CREATE PATHWAYS TO ACCESS, Research Monograph No. 15
16. Kavale, K.A. (2002), Mainstreaming to full inclusion: From orthogenesis to pathogenesis of an idea. International Journal of Disability, Development, and Education, page 49, 201-214.
17. Miles, S. (2000) Enabling Inclusive Education: Challenges and Dilemmas, paper presented at A Symposium on Development Policy entitled "Children with Disabilities and the Convention on the Rights of the Child" Gustav Stresemann Institute, Bonn, Germany, October 27-29, 2000, accessed at: http://www.eenet.org.uk/theory_practice/bonn_2.shtml

18. Miles, S. (2002) *Schools for All: Including disabled children in education, practice guidelines*, London: SCUK
19. Mukhopadhyay, S. (no date) *Rethinking About Inclusion: Emerging Area for Policy Research*, NUEPA
20. Mukhopadhyay, S. (2003) (ed) *National Seminar on Partnership of Government and Non-Government Organizations for Inclusive Education (October 15-17, 2003) Report*, New Delhi: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration
21. Panda, P. (2005) *Responsiveness of Pre-service Teacher Education Programme Towards Inclusive Education in India: Appraisal of Curriculum Dimensions and Practices*, National Council of Educational Research and Training paper presented at the Inclusive and Supportive Education Congress 2005, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow
22. Praisner, C. L. (2003), *Attitudes of elementary school principals toward the inclusion of students with disabilities*. *Exceptional Children*, page 69, 135-145.
23. *The Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education*. World Conference on Special Needs Education: Access and Quality, Salamanca, Spain, 7-10 June 1994. UNESCO and Ministry of Education and Science, Spain 1994.
24. Sanjeev, Kumar and Kumar, Khagendra, (2007) : *Inclusive Education in India*, *Electronic Journal for Inclusive Education*, Vol. 2, No. 2 [2007], Art. 7
25. SCUK (2004) *Education Programme of Save the Children (UK) in India: A Review using the Global Impact Monitoring Tool*, New Delhi: SCUK
26. Singal, N. (2005a) *Responding to difference: Policies to support 'inclusive education' in India*, paper presented at the Inclusive and Supportive Education Congress 2005, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow
27. Singal, N. (2005b) *Mapping the field of inclusive education: a review of the Indian literature*, *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 9 (4), October-December 2005, pp. 331-350
28. Strully, J., & Strully, C. (1996). *Friendships as an educational goal: What we have learned and where we are headed*. In W. Stainback & S. Stainback (Eds.), *Inclusion: A guide for educators*. Baltimore: Paul H. Brookes Publishing Co.
29. Thomas, P. (2004) *DFID and Disability: A Mapping of the Department for International Development and Disability Issues*, London: Disability Knowledge and Research, accessed at: <http://www.dfid.gov.uk/pubs/files/disability/dfid-and-disability.pdf>
30. Thorpe, V. & McKie, R. (2002) *The Rise and Fall of IQ*, in *The Observer*, March 17, 2002, accessed at: <http://observer.guardian.co.uk/focus/story/0,,668879,00.html>
31. Ture Johnsson, (2003) *Inclusive education CD developed for CBR Network's distance education programme*
32. WCEFA. (1990) *World Declaration on Education for All*, Inter-Agency Commission for the World Conference on Education for All, 1990
33. World Bank (2004) *Project Appraisal Document on a Proposed Credit of the Amount of SDR 334.9 million (US\$500 million Equivalent) to the Republic of India for an Elementary Education Project (Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan)*, Human Development Sector Unit, South Asia Region, accessed at: http://www-wds.worldbank.org/external/default/WDSContentServer/IW3P/IB/2004/04/02/000012009_20040402171429/Rendered/PDF/27703.pdf

